

Improving the water resistance of bismuth-based perovskite-inspired material for vapor-phase photocatalytic overall water splitting

Antonio J. Chacón-García¹, Herme G. Baldovi², Mike Pols³, Shuxia Tao³, Sofia Calero³, Sergio Navalón², Iñigo J. Vitorica-Yrezabal⁴, Antonio Rodríguez-Diéguez⁴, Hermenegildo García^{*5}, Patricia Horcajada^{*1}, Yolanda Pérez^{*1,6}

¹*Advanced Porous Materials Unit, IMDEA Energy Institute, Avda. Ramón y Cajal 3, 28935 Móstoles, Madrid, Spain*

²*Departamento de Química, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 València, Spain*

³*Material Simulation & Modelling, Department of Applied Physics and Science Education, Eindhoven University of Technology, 5600 MB, Eindhoven, The Netherlands*

⁴*Departamento Química Inorgánica, Universidad de Granada, 18071, Avenida de Fuente Nueva, Granada, Spain*

⁵*Instituto de tecnología química CSIC-UPV, Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), 46022, Spain*

⁶*COMET-NANO group, Departamento de Biología y Geología, Física y Química Inorgánica, ESCET, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, 28933 Móstoles, Madrid, Spain*

yolanda.cortes@urjc.es; patricia.horcajada@imdea.org; hgarcia@qim.upv.es

Supporting information

Figure S1. PXRD patterns of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials compared to their simulated patterns: a) IEF-19, b) IEF-19-Me, c) IEF-19-Et, d) IEF-19-Pr and e) IEF-19-But.

Table S1. Crystallographic data for the Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials

Identification code	IEF-19	IEF-19-Me	IEF-19-Et	IEF-19-Pr	IEF-19-But
Empirical formula	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ Bi ₂ I ₈ N ₂ O ₂	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ Bi ₂ I ₈ N ₂	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ Bi ₂ I ₈ N ₂	C ₂₂ H ₃₂ Bi ₂ I ₈ N ₂	C ₅₂ H ₈₈ Bi ₄ I ₁₆ N ₄
Formula weight	1657.46	1649.48	1705.58	1757.65	3635.58
Temperature/K	301.00	100.00	100.00	272.00	296.15
Crystal system	triclinic	triclinic	monoclinic	monoclinic	monoclinic
Space group	P-1	P-1	P2 ₁ /c	P2 ₁ /n	P2 ₁ /n
a/Å	7.717(2)	7.7623(5)	7.7086(3)	7.9084(4)	13.6871(9)
b/Å	9.962(3)	10.2176(6)	15.2004(6)	15.1739(8)	19.9692(13)
c/Å	10.391(2)	19.4300(13)	14.7037(6)	16.2500(7)	18.5070(11)
α/°	86.610(7)	87.738(2)	90	90	90
β/°	82.672(16)	83.079(2)	98.9500(10)	103.9920(10)	109.429(2)
γ/°	78.174(6)	87.146(2)	90	90	90
Volume/Å ³	775.0(4)	1527.04(17)	1701.91(12)	1892.16(16)	4770.3(5)
Z	1	2	2	2	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	3.551	3.587	3.328	3.085	2.531
μ/mm ⁻¹	84.677	19.600	17.592	15.829	12.562
F(000)	712.0	1416.0	1480.0	1536.0	3216.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.12 × 0.1 × 0.1	0.09 × 0.03 × 0.02	0.1 × 0.03 × 0.03	0.1 × 0.03 × 0.03	0.12 × 0.03 × 0.03
Radiation	CuKα (λ = 1.54178)	MoKα (λ = 0.71073)			
2θ range for data collection/°	8.584 to 132.946	4.226 to 57.55	5.35 to 50.83	5.95 to 50.736	4.506 to 50.692
Index ranges	-9 ≤ h ≤ 9, -11 ≤ k ≤ 11, -12 ≤ l ≤ 12	-10 ≤ h ≤ 10, -13 ≤ k ≤ 13, -26 ≤ l ≤ 26	-8 ≤ h ≤ 9, -16 ≤ k ≤ 18, -17 ≤ l ≤ 17	-9 ≤ h ≤ 9, -18 ≤ k ≤ 18, -19 ≤ l ≤ 18	-16 ≤ h ≤ 16, -24 ≤ k ≤ 23, -22 ≤ l ≤ 20
Reflections collected	11488	52430	17738	46638	151152
Independent reflections	2687 [R _{int} = 0.0612, R _{sigma} = 0.0642]	7906 [R _{int} = 0.0248, R _{sigma} = 0.0169]	3063 [R _{int} = 0.0263, R _{sigma} = 0.0183]	3313 [R _{int} = 0.0441, R _{sigma} = 0.0191]	8593 [R _{int} = 0.0338, R _{sigma} = 0.0131]
Data/restraints/parameters	2687/1/120	7906/0/239	3063/221/168	3313/213/210	8593/1249/578
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.022	1.185	1.061	1.089	1.051
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0590, wR ₂ = 0.1719	R ₁ = 0.0146, wR ₂ = 0.0328	R ₁ = 0.0280, wR ₂ = 0.0635	R ₁ = 0.0319, wR ₂ = 0.0687	R ₁ = 0.0390, wR ₂ = 0.0934
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0662, wR ₂ = 0.1798	R ₁ = 0.0151, wR ₂ = 0.0330	R ₁ = 0.0283, wR ₂ = 0.0636	R ₁ = 0.0335, wR ₂ = 0.0697	R ₁ = 0.0478, wR ₂ = 0.1025
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	2.67/-1.66	2.12/-1.25	2.33/-1.84	1.92/-1.29	1.23/-1.26

Table S2. Bi-I bond lengths for IEF-19.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Length
1	Bi1	I2*	3.102(1)
2		I3*	3.083(1)
3		I4*	2.975(2)
4		I5*	2.934(2)
5		I2**	3.238(1)
6		I3**	3.253(1)
*x, y, z; **-x, -y, -z			

Table S3. I-Bi-I and Bi-I-Bi bond angles for IEF-19

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Atom3	Angle
1	I2*	Bi1*	I3*	175.68(4)
2			I4*	86.56(3)
3			I5*	95.23(4)
4			I2**	86.15(3)
5			I3**	90.00(3)
6			I3*	I4*
7	I5*	88.39(4)		
8	I2**	91.32(3)		
9	I4*	I3**	86.18(3)	
10		I5*	96.99(4)	
11		I2**	168.21(4)	
12	I5*	I3**	88.56(3)	
13		I2**	92.89(4)	
14		I3**	172.58(4)	
15	I2**	I3**	82.19(3)	
16	Bi1*	I2	Bi1**	93.85(3)
17		I3		93.82(3)
*x, y, z; **-x, -y, -z				

Table S4. Bi-I bond lengths for IEF-19-Me.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Length
1	Bi1	I1*	2.9151(3)
2		I2*	2.9247(6)
3		I3*	3.2388(4)
4		I4*	3.3323(3)
5		I7*	3.2329(6)
6		I8*	2.9778(3)
7	Bi2	I3*	3.1721(3)
8		I4*	3.0502(3)
9		I5*	2.9141(6)
10		I6*	2.9586(3)
11		I8*	3.3289(5)
*x, y, z			

Table S5. I-Bi-I and Bi-I-Bi bond angles for IEF-19-Me

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Atom3	Angle
1	I1*	Bi1*	I2*	94.62(1)
2			I3*	84.22(1)
3			I4*	165.12(1)
4			I7*	92.31(1)
5			I8*	97.08(1)
6	I2*		I3*	99.78(1)
7			I4*	88.77(1)
8			I7*	173.06(1)
9	I3*		I8*	91.59(1)
10			I4*	80.92(1)
11			I7*	81.10(1)
12			I8*	168.44(1)
13	I4*		I7*	84.57(1)
14			I8*	97.31(1)
15	I7*		I8*	87.36(1)
16	Bi1*	I3	Bi2*	95.11(1)
17		I4		95.58(1)
18	I3*	Bi2*	I4*	86.51(1)
19			I5*	95.13(1)
20			I6*	172.87(1)
21			I7*	86.05(1)
22			I8*	86.25(1)
23	I4*		I5*	95.51(1)
24			I6*	91.25(1)
25			I7*	172.12(1)
26			I8*	93.36(1)
27	I5*		I6*	91.82(1)
28			I7*	87.73(1)
29			I8*	171.09(1)
30	I6*		I7*	95.84(1)
31			I8*	87.13(1)
32	I7*		I8*	83.58(1)
33	Bi2*	I7	Bi1*	93.55(1)
34		I8		94.08(1)

*x, y, z

Table S6. Bi-I bond lengths for IEF-19-Et.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Length
1	Bi1	I2*	3.2744(6)
2		I3*	2.9185(7)
3		I4*	3.0272(5)
4		I5*	2.8995(7)
5		I1**	3.2744(6)
6		I4**	3.2874(6)
*x, y, z **-x, -y, -z			

Table S7. I-Bi-I and Bi-I-Bi bond angles for IEF-19-Et.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Atom3	Angle	
1	I1*	Bi1*	I1**	85.33(1)	
2			I3*	87.43(2)	
3			I4*	174.32(2)	
4			I5*	95.04(2)	
5			I4**	89.30(1)	
6	I3*		I4*	95.86(2)	
7			I5*	95.30(2)	
8			I1**	167.46(2)	
9			I4**	88.09(2)	
10	I4*		I5*	89.28(2)	
11			I1**	90.59(1)	
12			I4**	86.19(1)	
13	I5*		I1**	95.52(2)	
14			I4**	174.60(2)	
15	I1**		I4**	81.60(1)	
16	Bi1*		I4*	Bi2*	93.81(1)
17			I1*		94.67(1)
*x, y, z **-x, -y, -z					

Table S8. Bi-I bond lengths for IEF-19-Pr.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Length
1	Bi1	I1*	3.1809(7)
2		I2*	3.0110(7)
3		I3*	2.8989(8)
4		I4*	2.9028(7)
5		I1**	3.3005(6)
6		I2**	3.3483(5)
*x, y, z **-x, -y, -z			

Table S9. I-Bi-I and Bi-I-Bi bond angles for IEF-19-Pr.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Atom3	Angle
1	I1*	Bi1*	I2*	173.16(2)
2			I3*	89.21(2)
3			I4*	94.20(2)
4			I1*	83.04(1)
5			I2*	90.52(2)
6	I2*	Bi1*	I3*	95.35(2)
7			I4*	90.40(2)
8			I1**	91.66(2)
9			I2**	84.45(2)
10	I3*	Bi1*	I4*	96.14(2)
11			I1**	168.30(2)
12			I2**	89.23(2)
13	I4*	Bi1*	I1**	93.17(2)
14			I2**	172.89(2)
15	I1**	Bi1*	I2**	82.12(1)
16	Bi1*	I1*	Bi1**	96.96(2)
27		I2*		95.55(2)
*x, y, z **-x, -y, -z				

Table S10. Bi-I bond lengths for IEF-19-But.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Length
1	Bi1	I1*	2.878(1)
2		I2*	2.8957(9)
3		I3*	2.861(1)
4		I4*	3.4480(9)
5		I8*	3.4230(6)
6	Bi2	I4*	3.0376(6)
7		I5*	2.8883(9)
8		I6*	3.1221(6)
9		I8*	3.3486(7)
10		I8**	3.3332(6)
*x, y, z **-x, -y, -z			

Table S11. I-Bi-I and Bi-I-Bi bond angles for IEF-19-But.

Number	Atom1	Atom2	Atom3	Angle
1	I1*	Bi1*	I6*	90.93(3)
2	I2*			171.97(3)
3	I3*			91.21(3)
4	I2*		I1*	93.19(3)
5	I3*			98.16(3)
6				I2*
7	I4*		I6*	85.25(2)
8			I1*	174.32(3)
9			I2*	90.11(3)
10			I3*	86.14(3)
11	I8*		I6*	81.51(2)
12			I1*	96.31(3)
13			I2*	91.18(2)
14			I3*	163.90(3)
15			I4*	78.99(2)
16	I4*	Bi2*	I8*	91.33(2)
17			I7*	91.79(2)
18			I5*	93.79(2)
19	I5*		I7*	96.63(2)
20			I8*	88.71(2)
21	I6*		I8*	85.93(2)
22			I7*	90.24(2)
23			I5*	93.61(2)
24	I7*		I4*	172.05(2)
25			I8*	173.62(2)
26	I8*		I8**	84.15(1)
27			I7**	90.50(2)
28			I5**	172.86(2)
29			I4**	86.22(2)
30			I6**	86.08(2)
31	Bi2*	I8*	Bi2**	95.85(2)
32			Bi1*	92.65(2)
33			Bi1**	94.66(2)
34	Bi1*	I6*	Bi2*	98.65(2)
35	Bi2*	I4*	Bi1*	100.11(2)

*x, y, z **-x, -y, -z

Fig. S2. ATR-FTIR spectra for Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials: a) IEF-19, b) IEF-19-Me c) IEF-19-Et, d) IEF-19-Pr and e) IEF-19-But compared to that free organic ligand (DAN).

Figure S3. Tauc plots for Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials: a) IEF-19, b) IEF-19-Me c) IEF-19-Et, d) IEF-19-Pr and e) IEF-19-But

Figure S4. Photoluminescence spectra of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials (excitation $\lambda = 405$ nm)

Figure S5. TD-XRD patterns of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials: a) IEF-19, b) IEF-19-Me c) IEF-19-Et, d) IEF-19-Pr and e) IEF-19-But.

Figure S6. PXRD patterns of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials: a) IEF-19 (fresh and after completely static-immersing in water for 3 days), b) IEF-19-Me c) IEF-19-Et, d) IEF-19-Pr and e) IEF-19-But (fresh and after completely static-immersing in water for 3 weeks)

Figure S7. PXRD patterns of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials (fresh and after 2 and 5 h suspension in water under stirring): a) IEF-19, b) IEF-19-Me, c) IEF-19-Et, d) IEF-19-Pr and e) IEF-19-But.

Figure S8. PXRD patterns of fresh IEF-19-Et and after 12 months under ambient conditions.

Figure S9. Organic DAN cations found in Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials. The cations form an IEF-19-R perovskite structure with (a) not, (b) methyl (Me), (c) ethyl (Et), (d) propyl (Pr) and (e) butyl (But) substituted. For the non-substituted DAN cation, the two types of headgroups are indicated as a and b, the same types of headgroups are also found in the other DAN cations.

Table S12. *k*-points grids used in bulk calculations of Bi-based perovskite-inspired materials.

Material	<i>k</i> -points
IEF-19	$4 \times 3 \times 3$
IEF-19-Me	$4 \times 3 \times 2$
IEF-19-Et	$4 \times 2 \times 2$
IEF-19-Pr	$4 \times 2 \times 2$
IEF-19-Bu	$4 \times 2 \times 2$

Figure S10. PXRD patterns of fresh IEF-19-Et, and IEF-19-Et after 3 and 4 cycles

Figure S11. Transient photocurrent density responses of the supported IEF-19-Et sample, which acts as a working electrode polarized at +0.4 V, during on-off irradiation cycles: UV-Vis irradiation (blue colour) and simulated sunlight irradiation (red colour).